

Summary of the Study on Employer's Experience with Hiring Highly/Middle/Low-Skilled Graduates on the Slovak Labor Market

Elaborated for the project **Learning Makes Sense (To dá rozum)**

By

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Conclusions and Executive Summary

Desired employee profile/Corporate requirements of job applicants

Job positions for highly-skilled staff

Concerning the desired employee profile, the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data shows that the most important criteria for hiring new staff to highly skilled jobs are the following: ability to learn, communication skills, motivation, basic PC skills and ability to work in a team. Employers consider the least important to be physical capabilities, manual skills, as well as formal education and professional certificates and licenses attained. For highly skilled jobs, most employers hire graduates without any work experience in the field. Although the majority of companies claim that graduates do not meet their expectations regarding work experience, during the recruitment process, they do not consider this requirement to be a priority. Furthermore, most employers state that graduates usually comply with their priority criteria only partially or not at all.

At a job interview, recruiters mostly assess graduates and their skills and knowledge at assessment centres, or using behavioural interviews and theoretical tests of their knowledge in specific fields. In the hiring process, employers also use various methods of psychometric testing to assess the personality of job applicants and their compatibility with certain job positions.

Regarding employers, their requirements of graduates, and how graduates comply with them, no significant differences were identified among employers based on ownership type, region, company size, industry (in cases with a sufficient number of observations).

Job positions for middle and low-skilled staff

The analysis shows that for middle and low-skilled job positions, employers consider the following criteria to be the most important for hiring new staff: ability to learn, ability to work in a team, motivation, and ability to adapt to changes. Employers place the lowest emphasis on foreign language skills, advanced PC skills, professional certificates and formal education attained.

Graduates comply with the abovementioned key requirements only partially or not at all, according to a majority of employers. Graduates applying for middle and low-skilled jobs comply the least with requirements on work experience in the field. For these job positions, employers requesting a certain level of formal education attained usually tend to request work experience in the specific field as well. Most employers hire graduates to middle and low-skilled job positions without prior work experience.

The data analysis shows that private companies with domestic ownership consider the following criteria to be important or crucial more frequently than companies with foreign ownership: work experience, basic PC skills, communication skills and analytical skills. There are no further differences in the hiring criteria among private companies with domestic and foreign ownership. The analysis suggests that Slovak employers are probably more demanding than their foreign counterparts.

Employers use mostly personal job interviews and assessment centres to assess knowledge and skills of job applicants. It is noteworthy that employers directly test the manual skills of applicants for middle and low-skilled jobs in their industry plants.

Co-operation between companies and schools

Job positions for highly-skilled staff

Most employers co-operate with schools; they usually offer student jobs and deliver lectures at schools. The analysis suggests that despite the existent co-operation there is no systemic feedback between schools and companies. The co-operation is usually initiated by employers and they tend to consider schools to be rather passive. Employers claim that the most frequent reason for the passivity of schools is the large number of competing companies trying to get into co-operation with schools, while schools only have the task of selecting the best offer. According to companies, another reason is the overall framework and funding of the education system, hindering co-operation between schools and companies. Therefore, employers are the main initiators of co-operation.

Employers also expressed both interest in and need for engagement in designing curricula for study programmes at universities. Companies consider graduates insufficiently prepared in terms of their practical skills and experience. They say that graduates have theoretical knowledge but cannot apply it in practice, they lack working habits and their adaptation process at work is rather lengthy. Companies express their interest in being more actively involved in the education process. They would appreciate more opportunities not only to identify talented students, but also to teach and train students in the fields specific to their business. Currently, companies offer student jobs in order to identify and train their prospective employees.

Companies offering highly skilled jobs co-operate with schools mainly to discover talent, to train prospective employees due to an insufficient labour supply and to shape the young generation. According to employers, they try to co-operate directly with students, because school curricula do not provide them with enough opportunities for engagement. Employers claim that the major advantage of their co-operation with schools is their branding among students, and the chance to inform them about interesting projects and career opportunities.

Employers evaluate their co-operation with schools rather negatively. In their co-operation, companies face several problems related to insufficient opportunities to engage students in working on specific issues related to particular company needs. Other problems relate to the general disinterest and passivity of universities in co-operating with companies, probably rooted in the unfavourable financing regulations set for schools. Co-operation with schools is further complicated by students lacking interest in building their careers, and lacking the motivation to acquire practical skills during their studies. Co-operation is also hindered by red tape and the inflexible system of school regulations currently in place.

The analysis found the following differences among companies and their perception of co-operation with schools, based on company size, region and company ownership type (due to the insufficient number of observations, no conclusions were drawn for the sector of economic activity):

Systemic feedback among companies and schools is least present for the large companies, while the mid-sized companies are most likely to provide systemic feedback on their co-operation with schools. There are no significant differences based on ownership type and regions.

Regarding types of co-operation, there are no differences among companies based on their size or ownership type. However, most companies operating in the Slovak capital of Bratislava tend to co-operate with schools by delivering lectures. Only half of companies operating outside of Bratislava deliver lectures at schools. On the other hand, companies operating outside of Bratislava are more likely to provide opportunities for professional internships.

Regarding problems in co-operation between companies and schools, the analysis showed that as much as 35% of private companies with foreign ownership perceive that school managements are unwilling to co-operate with their company. In contrary public or private companies with domestic ownership very rarely mention this problem.

Regarding reasons for co-operation, no differences were identified based on region or company size. Data also indicate that state-owned companies in Slovakia co-operate with schools mostly because they want to shape the young generation, with only a small fraction of these companies intending to find talent or train prospective employees through co-operation with schools. Private companies with both foreign and domestic ownership co-operate with schools mainly to find new talent during the time of their studies. It is noteworthy that no private company with foreign ownership indicated they intended to shape the young generation through co-operation with schools.

Job positions for middle and low-skilled staff

Employers with middle and low-skilled job positions co-operate with schools mainly by offering student jobs and professional training. Similar to highly skilled jobs, co-operation is mainly initiated by employers. They consider schools to be passive. In rare cases, qualitative research indicated school managements with active employees, and such schools were likely to be more proactive in contacting employers about potential co-operation.

A specific issue is the dual training system. Companies appreciate the opportunity to join the system and its legal regulation. Yet, they perceive problems in implementing dual training in practice. At the time of the survey, most companies perceived dual training to be a demanding task due to the administrative and organisational burden on both schools and themselves. Red tape was not the only problem; there were also ambiguities regarding the dual training procedures that schools and employers had to implement. At the time of the survey, uncertain funding posed another problem, because schools involved in the dual training system lost funding for practical education and therefore lacked interest in joining the dual training system. Quantitative data suggest that only 32% companies are involved in the dual training system. Where practical training is concerned, companies would appreciate more time for work with students. Most companies would like to reduce the time spent on classroom teaching and increase practical training carried out directly at their industry plants.

Employers hiring to middle and low-skilled job positions claim that graduates are not prepared for work. To some extent this is caused by a mismatch between study programmes and corporate needs, according to employers. Most companies promote a stronger link between school curricula and corporate needs. Companies are interested in engaging with students and schools through practical training at their own business plants as well as at schools. They would like to participate in curricula design so that the knowledge and skills attained by graduates reflect corporate needs. Another reason why businesses intend to co-operate with schools in their curricula design is that companies strive to

have prospective employees mastering work habits, discipline and the particular technologies used at their own company.

Most companies co-operate with schools in order to train new employees due to a labour market shortage. Also, companies co-operate with schools to find talent and shape the young generation. Companies benefit from co-operation with schools: they can train prospective employees and can present themselves to students as a potential employer.

Most companies offering middle and low-skilled jobs do not share their feedback on co-operation with schools. However, a group of these companies have established systemic feedback with schools, and it seems to work better than at companies offering highly skilled jobs. Here also companies experience a passive approach from schools. In most cases, the feedback process is initiated by companies, and schools only passively receive it.

Based on the qualitative and quantitative data, companies consider their co-operation with schools to be insufficient. The main barriers to co-operation are the passive approach from schools, low motivation of students to co-operate, and the ineffective school financing system, coupled with the inefficiencies of the dual training system. Companies stressed that they lacked opportunities to shape the school curricula, and that there was inadequate time allocated for the practical training of students.

Co-operation with schools is hindered by several factors: low interest of students in building their careers, red tape for businesses, and the unwillingness of schools to co-operate with companies.

Companies offering middle and low-skilled jobs pointed out several good practice cases of co-operation with schools. A common trait of these examples was that a school enabled the company to shape school curricula, design a new school subject and provide full-scale practical training of students. A good co-operation also involves vivid feedback and two-way communication between schools and companies.

The following differences in co-operation between companies and schools were identified in data based on region, ownership type and company size. Among companies offering middle and low-skilled jobs, large companies and private companies with foreign ownership most frequently co-operate with schools in preparing graduates for the labour market. There are no differences regarding whether the company resides in Bratislava or elsewhere.

Regarding the existence of systemic feedback, there are no differences based on region, ownership type, sector of economic activity or company size. Regarding forms of co-operation, no differences could be identified based on region, ownership type, sector of economic activity or company size due to the insufficient number of observations. Regarding problems in co-operation between schools and companies, companies operating in Bratislava differ from the rest of the sample. Companies operating in Bratislava more frequently claim red tape is a problem compared to companies outside Bratislava.

Also, companies operating in Bratislava co-operate with schools because they intend to find talent during their studies and want to shape the young generation. Companies outside Bratislava also intend to find talent, but their second most frequent reason for co-operation with schools is to train prospective employees due to a shortage on the labour market. Ownership type plays a role in

employers' reasons for co-operation. Private companies with domestic ownership start co-operation in order to find talent, while only a minority of them intends to train prospective employees. However, half of the private companies with foreign ownership co-operate with schools to train prospective employees, while only a minority intend to find talent during their study.

Assessing the labour market supply and how it is matching employers' needs

Job positions for highly-skilled staff

When hiring to job positions for highly-skilled staff, the major problem perceived by employers is that most graduates only partially match company requirements for highly-skilled job positions. Graduates do not meet key requirements set by employers, and their motivation for career development is insufficient. Companies have to invest more funds in training graduates, and additional funds need to be allocated for brand building and attracting students and graduates to become their prospective employees.

The most important employers' criteria for hiring new staff are the following: ability to learn, motivation, communication skills, basic PC skills, ability to work in a team, knowledge in a particular field and ability to adapt to changes. According to most employers, graduates usually meet these criteria only partially. Graduates receive the best assessment from companies for their basic PC skills, and the worst assessment for their motivation. Concerning motivation, employers say that graduates do not have a proactive approach and lack modesty, while their salary expectations are too high. Regarding communication skills, employers perceive that graduates have gaps in their presentation and argumentation skills. Furthermore, companies perceive graduates to be inflexible and uncooperative in teamwork.

When employers compare graduates now to those a decade earlier, they consider current graduates to be slightly better in foreign language skills and computer literacy. However, they tend to be inferior in soft skills (communication, leadership, argumentation and presentation skills, along with the ability to work with various personalities in a team). Employers find graduates inadequately prepared for work in practice, and this status has not changed over the past decade. Another trend employers perceive is that university graduates tend to be less specialised and their education is more broad than thoroughly specialised. Some companies view this trend favourably, because students tend to seek context and their knowledge is more general and less narrow. However, some employers criticise this trend, and would appreciate if students mastered a specific field of study and a particular technology.

When summarising the quantitative and qualitative data, most companies assess graduates rather negatively; graduates match their needs only partially or not at all. However, graduates with work experience who attended internships or sought out other active career building opportunities at a potential employer are assessed as almost or fully matching the criteria. Also here, the insufficient co-operation between schools and companies plays a role.

Using qualitative data, the analysis focused on employers' assessment of university graduates at various stages and their individual skills and knowledge. Companies assess graduates with a bachelor's degree (completed 1st stage of tertiary education) as immature and lacking specific knowledge and communication, argumentation and presentation skills. Most employers said that graduates with a bachelor's degree are hired mainly for administrative positions not requiring any particular

specialisation or expertise. Employers prefer master's graduates (completed 2nd stage of tertiary education) and consider them more mature and possessing more specialised knowledge. Some employers appreciate that master's graduates have work experience gained at student jobs or internships. PhD graduates are demanding employees searching for deeper meaning in their work, according to employers. Many companies consider them overqualified and not suitable for practical work. Employers associate this level of education with academia and research. PhD graduates are perceived by companies to be individuals overly focused on theory, and prefer not to hire them to job positions for highly-skilled staff.

Companies seek to invest more resources in developing soft skills, such as assertive communication, active listening, negotiation and argumentation skills, problem solving, and communication in conflicts. They seek to develop the organisation and time management skills of graduates. Many companies train their staff in other work-related skills to familiarise them with specific technologies, software standards or processes.

According to both quantitative and qualitative data, most companies perceive that graduates of the same field of study but from different schools to have varying levels of skills and knowledge. These differences are greater for highly-skilled job positions than for middle and low-skilled jobs. Such differences are most prevalent in technical and IT fields. Some universities are better at preparing students regarding up-to-date programming languages, technologies or processes. The foreign language skills of graduates vary as well. Some university graduates can easily communicate in English, while others are only advanced learners.

The issue of whether university graduates possess up-to-date knowledge spans the whole qualitative study. Employers tended to be critical on this topic. They were unsatisfied that graduates entering the labour market lack practical skills, and their theoretical knowledge, despite being extensive, is not up-to-date with current trends. Employers indicate that teachers themselves should learn more about new trends, and should actively communicate with professionals in the field.

However, employers consider graduates from universities abroad to be better prepared. During the interviews, respondents reflected that graduates from the Czech universities worked better in teams, were more self-confident and had clear career goals, along with better presentation, argumentation and active listening skills. Also, they claimed graduates from universities abroad had up-to-date knowledge and could effectively link their theoretical knowledge with practice.

The following differences among employers were identified regarding the supply of graduates in the labour market: Regarding company size, the majority (65%) of small companies consider that graduates match their requirements partially or not at all, while most mid-sized companies (69%) consider they comply partially or fully with their criteria. Also, half of the large companies (51%) consider that graduates comply partially or fully with their criteria.

By ownership type, most Slovak state-owned companies (73%) and private companies with foreign ownership (57%) consider that graduates comply partially or fully with their criteria. However, private companies with domestic ownership seem to be more demanding, and most of them consider that graduates match their requirements partially or not at all (55%).

Most small-sized companies (61%) and large companies (62%) claim that graduates do not match their requirements on work experience. On the other hand, less than half of the mid-sized companies (47.5%) claim that graduates do not match their requirements on work experience.

Regarding the criteria least fulfilled by graduates, the following differences were identified in the analysis: Private companies with domestic ownership claimed a majority of graduates (54%) do not comply with their expectations regarding professional certificates and licenses. This is less frequent for state-owned domestic companies (35%) and private companies with foreign ownership (43%). Most employers, independently of company size, ownership type and region, perceived graduates of the same field of study, but at different schools, to have varying levels of skills and knowledge.

Job positions for middle and low-skilled staff

The major challenge when hiring to middle and low-skilled job positions is the lack of both qualified and motivated workers. Employers have enough job applicants, but only a minority of them are ready to adapt quickly and perform well at work. According to employers, it is not only difficult to find the right employees, but also to train, motivate and retain them.

For middle and low-skilled job positions, employers consider the following to be the most important criteria: ability to learn, ability to work in a team, motivation, and ability to adapt to changes. Out of these key criteria, graduates comply the least with motivation and ability to adapt to changes. However, they comply with most of the other criteria.

Overall, most employers do not consider graduates applying for middle and low-skilled jobs to be suitable. In the analysed qualitative and quantitative data, employers assess graduates more as not suitable and not ready for practical work. Graduates do not match the requirements and expectations of employers; employers are willing to train graduates, but they often adopt a passive approach to their career development.

For middle and low-skilled job positions, employers do not seek graduates with only basic education. They consider them immature, and unable to process information, solve more difficult tasks and familiarise themselves with basic processes and technologies. Most attractive for employers are graduates from secondary vocational schools with a school leaving exam or vocational certificate. They are more mature, specialised in a particular field and have theoretical and sometimes also practical experience in it. Although companies perceived grammar school graduates to be prospective university students, and considered education at grammar schools to be general, some employers assessed these graduates in positive terms and appreciated their analytical thinking, ability to learn fast and their growth potential. It seems that as long as graduates are motivated, employers appreciate that and are even willing to invest in a long-term adaptation process.

At secondary schools also, employers perceived graduates of the same field of study but from different schools to have varying levels of skills and knowledge. The main difference is that secondary schools enable the matching of curricula to employers' needs, so companies can systematically co-operate with schools and students and train their prospective staff. The dual training system plays a role here, and despite its red tape and administrative burden, companies assess it positively.

Employers criticised the level of up-to-date knowledge and sufficiency of practical training for graduates. Especially, employers were critical of graduates not mastering technologies used at their own companies. As a result, companies hire employees and have to train them themselves, because the education system is not effectively fulfilling its role and does not grant companies with enough opportunities and funds to engage in the education and training of students.

The following differences regarding the supply of graduates in the labour market were identified in data based on region, ownership type and company size: Most mid-sized (84%) and large companies (56%) claim that graduates do not match their requirements on work experience.

Also, the majority of large companies (55%) claim that graduates do not meet their requirements on foreign language skills. This issue is not so significant at mid-sized companies; at 42% of them graduates do not meet their requirements on foreign language skills. Large companies seem to be more demanding in terms of foreign language skills, also for middle and low-skilled job positions.

It is noteworthy that the highest proportion of graduates not meeting requirements on foreign language skills was at private companies with foreign ownership (60%). However, only 21% of private companies with domestic ownership claimed graduates did not meet their requirements on foreign language skills.

Regarding the motivation of graduates, private companies with foreign ownership seemed to be the most critical; 41% claimed graduates did not meet their requirements on motivation. This figure is only 27% for private companies with domestic ownership.

Assessment of the education system framework by employers

Job positions for highly-skilled staff

Most applicants to job positions for highly-skilled staff comply with the company criteria related to formal education, according to the data analysis. However, formal education is not a key requirement for companies. Companies appreciate relevant and long-term work experience more than formal education. They are even willing to hire a secondary school graduate to a position for highly-skilled staff, if that person has interesting work experience. Although companies have not expressed explicit requirements on formal education attained, their most preferred candidates for highly-skilled job positions among graduates are those with a master's degree. Usually, no specific requirements on certificates and licences were mentioned by companies. However, positions in the health-care industry are legally regulated, and only applicants with a specific education, attestation procedure or length of service in specific health-care facilities are hired. Some employers in the IT industry request certificates or licenses related to programming languages (Java developers), databases (SAP, SQL) or software in the case of graduates without any work experience.

Another issue is whether companies hire applicants with a higher level of education attained to job positions where a lower level would suffice (the question was aimed specifically at hiring applicants with a master's degree to positions where a bachelor's degree would suffice; there is an insufficient number of observations on PhD graduate students). In most cases, companies do not hire applicants with a higher university degree to positions where a lower degree would suffice. However, companies that admitted such a practice explained it thus: they consider graduates with a master's degree to be

more mature, and there are enough job applicants with a master's degree applying for bachelor's degree positions, and companies have a broad choice. It is impossible to track this phenomenon in time, based on the available data.

During the interviews, companies made several criticisms of the quality of university education and its stages. In the case of bachelor's studies, employers criticise the education for being too general and lacking in professional specialisation. Graduates are not ready to enter the job market smoothly because they are immature and have gaps in their theoretical and practical skills. In the case of master's studies, companies are critical of the practical skills of graduates. Due to gaps in their practical skills, employers have to devote more attention, mentoring and training to them. Moreover, employers point out that schools do not develop soft skills in their students and the theoretical knowledge provided to students is sometimes not up-to-date. Employers claim that it is difficult to create adequate working conditions for PhD graduates, in such a way that they are satisfied and their knowledge is fully exploited. For employers, PhD are perceived more as scientific staff, and they cannot offer them full-time employment. External co-operation on individual projects seems to be a better option for their engagement with companies.

For companies, the most promising employees are graduates with a master's degree. They are more mature as people and possess a professional specialisation, although companies have to initially invest more resources in their career progress.

Data analysis indicated that the most striking mismatch between the labour market & employer needs and education system outcomes is **the lack of practical skills graduates would need at job positions for highly-skilled staff**. Graduates are not familiar with new technologies and their knowledge is not up-to-date in certain areas. Also, graduates have unrealistic expectations and companies partially blame schools for this. Often, graduates expect that even without work experience they could be hired to managerial positions or highly specialised job positions. Graduates also have excessive salary demands. Another deficit noted by most companies are underdeveloped soft skills – presentation, argumentation and negotiation skills, teamwork, communication in conflicts, problem solving, ability to co-operate with various personalities in a team, and ability to adapt to changes. Graduates cannot communicate or present in English on professional issues, and sometimes even simple communication in a foreign language poses a problem. For technical positions, companies often come across graduates who do not communicate in English well, or even not at all. Regarding developers and programmers, IT companies complain that graduates do not master certain programming languages and that they later have to learn them on their own or at specialised courses.

Companies consider state education policies to be inadequate and not reflecting labour market needs. Employers mostly lack opportunities to link school education with practice and design curricula. According to companies, they have no opportunity to participate in education policy development and are not involved in this process.

Regarding evaluation of the education system framework, there are no differences between companies based on region (Bratislava, outside capital), ownership type, sector of economic activity or company size. Most companies of all types claimed that graduates do not have up-to-date knowledge and skills and lack practical experience. Furthermore, most companies of all types believed that schools do not put maximum effort into preparing students for the labour market, and in general,

schools do not prepare enough graduates with a relevant qualifications. There is an insufficient number of observations to draw conclusions on the level of sector of economic activity.

Job positions for middle and low-skilled staff

The analysis indicated that applicants with only basic education attained are not suitable for companies offering job positions for middle and low-skilled staff. Employers request at least a vocational certificate. Graduates from secondary vocational schools are the most attractive for companies, as they possess the best theoretical and practical knowledge (though still not sufficient) compared to other applicants from basic schools, 3-year vocational programmes or grammar schools.

Usually, companies hire to middle and low-skilled job positions mostly graduates with a higher degree of education than necessary. Almost half of the companies hire university graduates to positions where a secondary school-leaving exam would suffice, and 40% of companies hire graduates with such an exam to positions where a vocational certificate is sufficient. More detailed inquiry into employers' motivation for such practices (hiring graduates possessing a higher degree than necessary for a job position) suggests that most employers consider graduates with a higher level of education attained to be more mature. Also, many companies claim there are enough applicants with a higher level of education attained so they prefer them, and that these graduates have better knowledge. Almost a third of companies (30%) hiring applicants with a secondary school-leaving exam to positions where a vocational certificate is sufficient claimed that graduates with a vocational certificate do not meet requirements on professional skills.

Companies evaluate the quality of individual levels of education intended for middle and low-skilled job positions as inadequate. According to companies, this problem has its roots in primary school education, and they suggest there should be more psychologists and career advisers at schools to deal in more detail with the personal and intellectual abilities of students, and their preferred school subjects or fields of study. Employers also indicate that admission criteria to grammar schools are too lax, and as a result, the worse performing students enter secondary vocational schools. Moreover, employers complain that the overall quality of education on 3-year and 4-year vocational programmes is inadequate, and theory is not linked to practice in them. Employers also noted that graduates have excessive salary expectations and overestimate their skills match for specialised positions requiring extensive experience.

Companies criticised the practical training organised by schools themselves and in co-operation with employers. According to employers, schools often do not want to waive their own practical training, because their funding is linked to it. If schools let employers organise practical education, schools loose funding. This issue is also relevant to the dual training system. Companies view it positively, but criticise its unclear funding. Practical training organised solely by schools is inadequate and does not reflect up-to-date trends and technologies.

For middle and low-skilled job positions, **the most striking problem is the lack of practical training for students, and their theoretical knowledge, which is not up-to-date, according to employers.** Some companies in the energy industry stated that there is a lack of graduates in the heavy-current field, where manual skills are also required. In general, employers indicate that students tend to avoid positions requiring manual work. They add that lax admission criteria to grammar schools and business academies result in only low-performing students with low motivation and interest in their personal

and career development entering vocational schools. Companies point out that graduates lack regulatory certificates for working with forklifts and certificates for working with heavy-current. Employers are dissatisfied with students' manual skills and their low motivation, along with their outdated knowledge and lack of practical training at schools, regardless of the sector of economic activity, company size and ownership type.

Employers surveyed tended to be critical of **state education policies, claiming they are inadequate and do not reflect labour market needs**. Employers interviewed often stated they are interested in participating in education policy-making and designing school curricula in such a way that they match with employers' requests.

Regarding evaluation of the education system framework, there are no differences between companies based on region (Bratislava, outside capital), ownership type, economic industry or company size. Most companies of all types claimed that graduates do not have up-to-date knowledge and skills and lack practical experience. Furthermore, most companies of all types believed that schools do not put maximum effort into preparing students for the labour market, and in general, schools do not prepare enough graduates with the relevant qualifications. There is an insufficient number of observations to draw conclusions on the level of the sector of economic activity.